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Entrepreneurship Education Strategies Required by Undergraduate Students for Skills Acquisition in Universities in North Central, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined entrepreneurship education strategies required by undergraduate students for skills acquisition in universities in North Central, Nigeria. Four objectives were achieved in the study. Population for this study included all undergraduate students and entrepreneurship education lecturers of two universities in the North Central, Nigeria namely; University of Abuja and Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi, Benue State. A sample size of 284 respondents was used for the study. Structured questionnaire was used for data collection. Mean, standard deviation, percentages, t-test and regression analysis were used for data analysis. Findings of the study revealed that the level at which entrepreneurship education is implemented in universities in North Central, Nigeria is very low. Findings also revealed a significant relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial skills. Also, the findings revealed challenges affecting full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities. Finally, findings of the study revealed strategies for enhancing full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in North Central, Nigeria. The study concludes that appropriate strategies could be adopted to enhance full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in the North Central, Nigeria. It was recommended that the universities should place much emphasis on entrepreneurship education considering the fact that it serves as a tool for entrepreneurial skills acquisition. The government should ensure that entrepreneurship education is properly funded for enhanced entrepreneurial skills acquisition in universities in the North Central, Nigeria.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education, Strategies, Undergraduate Students, Skills Acquisition

INTRODUCTION

Skill development is important to every individual. This is because the skills allow people to improve attributes and qualities vital to earn a living. Teaching an innovation process to exploit a business opportunity by applying entrepreneurial learning (knowledge and skills) has been considered an important academic activity in universities. Entrepreneurship skills are essential in positioning entrepreneurs to identify opportunities, make effective decisions, turn their ideas into reality, overcome challenges, and properly allocate resources to achieve goals and succeed.

The concept of entrepreneurship seems difficult to clearly define. Many scholars view it in different ways. For instance, Shuaibu, Kamin, Isa and Cleduma (2020), posited that the psychologists (behaviourists) view it as “the need for achievement, perceived locus of control, and risk-taking propensity”. On the other hand, the economists look at it as bringing together the factors of production (land, labour, capital, and entrepreneur) and

bearing the risk of buying at a certain price and selling at uncertain prices. The sociologists view it as the ability to recognize and act upon market opportunities in order to provide social services.

Entrepreneurship education refers to a collection of formalized teaching process that informs, educates, and trains anyone concerned in business establishment (Arnaut, 2020). Entrepreneurship education may also be defined as a pedagogical process which supports entrepreneurial activities, behaviors and outlook. According to Shuaibu, Kamin, Isa and Cleduma (2020), entrepreneurship education is the willingness and ability of an individual to seek out investment opportunities in an environment and be able to establish and run an enterprise successfully. It is the process of creating something different with value by devoting the necessary time and effort, assuming the accompanying financial, psychological, and social risk, and receiving the resulting rewards of monetary and personal satisfaction. Shuaibu et al., (2020) further stressed that entrepreneurship education is considered as an attempt to create value through recognition of business opportunities, communicative, and management skills to mobilize human, financial and material resources necessary to bring a project to function. Entrepreneurship education is the process of identifying, developing and bringing a vision to life. The vision May be an innovative idea, an opportunity, or simply a better way to do something. The end result of this process is the creation of a new venture, formed under conditions of risk and considerable uncertainty (Hisrich in Shuaibu et al., 2020).

Entrepreneurship education teach students how to think like an entrepreneur; enable students to create jobs, contribute to the economy; develop a sense of social responsibility; teach students how to be innovate, create jobs and start their own businesses in order to have a growing economy in the future, and enhances practical and leadership skills acquisition. Skill is very important in the life of every citizen (Nawaz, 2022).

Entrepreneurship education seeks to provide students with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of settings. Entrepreneurship education focuses on the development of skills or attributes that enable the realization of opportunity, where management education is focused on the best way to operate existing hierarchies. Both approaches share an interest in achieving "profit" in some form (which in non-profit organizations or government can take the form of increased services or decreased cost or increased responsiveness to the customer/citizen/client) (Paolucci, Sansone and Fiore, 2019). Entrepreneurship education has the mandate to equip the youths with functional knowledge and skill to build up their character, attitude and vision. It has vital role in developing eco-system that promotes innovation (European Union, 2006). Gautam (2015) highlighted that the importance of entrepreneurship education for providing the base for innovation and creating a value system; and developing entrepreneurial culture, which drives wealth creation and gives further push to innovations. According to Nawaz (2022), entrepreneurship education teach students how to think like an entrepreneur; enable students to create jobs, contribute to the economy; develop a sense of social responsibility; teach students how to be innovate, create jobs and start their own businesses in order to have a growing economy in the future, and enhances practical and leadership skills acquisition. Skill is very important in the life of every citizen.

It has been observed in the North Central, Nigeria that today, there are many unemployed graduates. One of the problems of the education system of Nigeria is that it lacks transfer of skills to the students. The education system is based on theories. The most number of unemployed is found in North Central, Nigeria. According to International Labour Congress, in 2013, Africa had the highest unemployment rate (Nawaz, 2022). The truth remains that the major causes of the unemployment among these vibrant youths is lack of skill to back up what they learnt from their institutions of learning. When these graduates were still in school, they did not border to learn at least one single skill, maybe that which is related in public organization needs. If they have learnt any skill at all, the rate of unemployment will be reduced among youths in the North Central, Nigeria. A skilled employee is more likely to advance in his career in terms of job opportunities, promotions and job retention than those without relevant skills. A skill acquired individual is always self-employed. For Nigeria to be economically self-reliant, necessary action must be taken to diversify the economy and as well encourage the youths to embrace self-employment through skills acquisition, entrepreneurship, self-reliance and financial empowerment.

An observation by the researcher revealed that much emphasis is laid on academic excellence in the North Central universities leaving students with poor entrepreneurial skills. Even when they are graduated, they lack

the necessary skills to business management skills, communication and listening, critical and creative thinking skills, strategic thinking and planning skills, branding, marketing, and networking skills, entrepreneurial skills in the workplace, teamwork and leadership skills, time management and organizational skills, sales skills and stress management skills. This category of graduates also finds it difficult to be self sustained. This study therefore examines the entrepreneurship education strategies required by undergraduate students for skills acquisition in universities in North Central, Nigeria.

Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the entrepreneurship education strategies required by undergraduate students for skills acquisition in universities in North Central, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the level of implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in North Central, Nigeria
2. Determine the relationship between entrepreneurship education and planning, business, communication, critical and creative thinking, management and leadership skills
3. Examine the challenges affecting full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in North Central, Nigeria
4. Identify strategies for enhancing full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in North Central, Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

Importance of Entrepreneurship Skills

Entrepreneurial education has a positive impact on increasing startup rates (Tung, 2011). It also leads to increased knowledge about how to launch and manage a new business venture (Casimir and Schaper in Larimi, Chizari, Mulder and Biemans, 2012). Entrepreneurship education helps students to gain experience in a real business context by fostering favourable attitudes toward entrepreneurial activities, develops perception of self-efficacy of students, raises the level of students' entrepreneurial intentions and stimulates students to choose an entrepreneurial career. Tung in Larimi et al., (2012) posited that entrepreneurial education is one of the main elements that contribute significantly to the increase of entrepreneurial attitudes. The authors further stressed that students are taught how to interact with their environment to identify an opportunity and start a new venture (Larimi et al., 2012).

Entrepreneurship skills are essential in positioning entrepreneurs to identify opportunities, make effective decisions, turn their ideas into reality, overcome challenges, and properly allocate resources to achieve goals and succeed. The importance of entrepreneurship skills lies in: encouraging social change and improving lives; creating employment opportunities for others; driving economic growth and opening new markets and industries; improving the quality of life with new ideas and building functional products or services; providing opportunities for personal and professional growth, as well as financial rewards; enhancing one's capacity to work efficiently alone, as well as in collaboration; and reaching the desired goals and achieving excellent results

Characteristics of Entrepreneurship

According to Shuaibu et al. (2020), the characteristics of an entrepreneur refer to characteristics, traits, qualities, and features of an entrepreneur. These are: self-confidence – which belief in own ability, individuality, optimism, and independence; risk-taking – which accommodates all challenges of the business; originality – that deals with innovative, creative, resourceful, versatile, knowledgeable and flexible (open-minded); leadership – which gets along well with others, responsive to suggestions and criticism, concern for others and excellent communication; hardwork-drive – that puts longer hours than usual in business; independence – which emphasises autonomous and being their own boss; goal setting – that sets goals and work towards achieving them; task result-oriented – who are persons who are inclined to achievement orientation, profit orientation, energetic, and initiative; strong will-power – who are persons with persistence, perseverance, and determination; and self-reliance - that urges one to do it alone (want to carry it out).

The diagrammatic representation of the characteristics of an entrepreneur is shown below:

Reason for Introduction of Entrepreneurship in Universities

Entrepreneurship education is regarded as a critical component of our educational curriculum because of the obvious need to generate alternative sources of employment (Amaewhule, 2014). It is the engine of development in Nigeria. Entrepreneurship education offers a solution. It seeks to prepare people, particularly youths to be responsible, enterprising individuals who become entrepreneurs or entrepreneurial thinkers by immersing them in real life learning experiences where they can take risks, manage the results and learn from the outcomes. According to Ubogu (2020), entrepreneurship education trains students in higher education institutions including those with disabilities, learn organizational skills, such as time management, leadership development and interpersonal skills, all of which are highly transferable skills sought by employers.

Entrepreneurship Education and Skills Development

The purpose of introduction of entrepreneurship in universities is to educate students on skills acquisition and the knowledge needed before taking a decision on embarking on a business venture. It helps to enhance the creation of job opportunities and achieve economic growth (Boma, Godpower and Kire, 2019). As noted by Ukata and Adejola (2018), the introduction of entrepreneurship education is worldily accepted as one of the greatest instruments for achieving economic and development as well as employment creation. Similarly, entrepreneurship education is included education curriculum because of its importance in developing and growing the economy. Dambo, Akpelu, and Nwiyorin Boma, Godpower and Kire (2019 asserted that the greatest tool toward overcoming the persistent economic challenges is making sure that we exploit the entrepreneurship programmes available within our disposal and also making it active because if we have many entrepreneurs, jobs will never be a challenge in the society. For these reasons, any country is not ready to embrace opportunity of making its citizens self-reliant will always suffer the challenges of high unemployment.

It is believed that entrepreneurship education opens the mind of people to acquire the right ideas, skills and managerial ability that will help in job creation (Boma, Godpower and Kire, 2019. To achieve this, people are given the proper training for the available jobs and in order to open their own businesses. The level of preparation given to any student is determined by the level of their readiness to execute a given task on a particular field. According to Amaewhule, (2014), entrepreneurship is considered as a vital ingredient for economic development of any nation. For any nation to achieve any economic growth, the nation must embrace entrepreneurship and make sure that the students and youths are fully engaged in entrepreneurship training.

Factors affecting Entrepreneurship Education in Universities in Nigeria

There are many problems facing full implementation of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria. Ubogu (2013) noted that under-funding undermines the quality entrepreneurship education. The author stressed that lack of

facilities for proper training for acquisition of entrepreneurial skills. These facilities include adequate teaching materials, equipment, laboratories and workshops. The problem of awareness and motivation within the institutions also stampedes entrepreneurship education. Dearth of lecturers of entrepreneurship, who have not been trained from the start in that field, suffers the programme. As a consequence, they may be unaware of the right approach to entrepreneurship teaching. The teachers themselves are not skilled and do not realize that the education policy allows them freedom to hire professionals (entrepreneurs) to teach some skills to the students (Ubogu, 2010).

Strategies for achieving Full Implementation of Entrepreneurship Education in Universities

The best way to ensure full implementation of entrepreneurship business projects while in schools (Akhuemokhan et al., in Ubogu, 2023). According to Olajide (2019) become job seekers is an underutilization of training students who graduate only the country's human resources hence, there needs to be a coordinated policy support to deepen entrepreneurship education in universities. Ubogu (2011) asserted that in order to achieve the policy thrusts of the Federal Government of Nigeria; targeting the universities for spinning off entrepreneurship spirit and culture, a good strategy of presidential committee on the introduction and implementation of entrepreneurship education in all universities was set up.

Also, Azuka and Azuka (2013) listed the strategies to achieve a functional entrepreneurship education for national development. These include adoption of innovative methods to train teachers in entrepreneurship; setting up of short-term exchanges of entrepreneurship teachers between the institutions of higher education in order to disseminate best practice and teaching methods; establishment of a think tank group, including the ministries of education, employment, science and technology, to determine how entrepreneurship can be integrated into the education system across primary, secondary, and higher education, adopting legislation supporting relations between private business and universities, including allowing faculty members to work part-time with business; an introduction to entrepreneurship and self-employment should be offered as part of career guidance and establishing job creation offices in each of the states in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Area of the Study

The study was conducted in North Central, Nigeria. The North Central Nigeria is a region carved out from the west, around the confluence of the River Niger and the River Benue. It is a region stretching around central Nigeria longitudinally and forming a transition zone between Northern and Southern Nigeria. The North Central Nigeria is made up of the six states namely: Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Plateau and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja.

Design

The study employed the use of Comparative research design. This is because the study aimed at investigating the similarities and differences between the responses of two groups. The design looks at the two groups and how they relate to another in their responses. Since the design is qualitative and quantitative, it was found suitable for the study.

Population

Population for this study comprised all undergraduate students, Entrepreneurship lecturers of University of Abuja and Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi, Benue State. Lecturers were used because they are responsible for imparting the knowledge on entrepreneurship education to students. The students were used because they are directly involved in acquisition of entrepreneurship education. It was therefore believed that this category of respondents would supply the needed information making inferences for the study.

Sample Size

The sample size of 284 respondents was used for the study. Purposive sampling technique was adopted to select 100 students from University of Abuja and 100 students Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi, Benue State. The whole 35 Lecturers University of Abuja and 49 lecturers of Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi who teach of entrepreneurship education were purposively used making a total of 284 respondents for the study.

Instrument for the Study

Data for the study was collected using structured questionnaire. The instrument was divided into two parts; part ‘A’ sought to elicit information on demographic characteristics of the respondents while part ‘B’ dwell on objectives of the study and was sub-divided into section A to D. The instrument had restricted responses of very high extent (VHE), high extent (HE), low extent (LE and very low extent (VLE), strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). These had corresponding values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data for the study was analysed using both descriptive statistical tools of percentages mean, standard deviation and inferential statistical tolls of analysis of variance (ANOVA) and linear regression. The reason for use of ANOVA is because it compares more than two groups simultaneously to determine whether a relationship exists between them. Regression analysis was used because the study also aims to determine the interaction effect of entrepreneurship education on skills acquisition. The result of the ANOVA and regression allow the study to analyze the data collected from lecturers and students to assess the variability between and within groups, and the interaction effect between dependent and independent variables.

RESULTS

Fig. 2: Chart showing percentage of respondents

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Lecturers and Students on the Level of Implementation of Entrepreneurship Education in Universities

S/N	Item Statement	N ₁	N ₂	\bar{x}_1	\bar{x}_2	SD ₁	SD ₂	Remarks
1	At what level does your university recommend students to National Directorate of Employment (NDE) for training?	84	200	1.24	1.45	0.77	0.8	Low
2	What is the level of students’ participation in Industrial Attachment or Student Industrial Working Experience Scheme (SIWES)?	84	200	1.27	1.57	0.72	0.98	Low
3	How does your university engage students in vocational and technical training?	84	200	1.46	1.33	0.92	0.73	Low
4	What is the extent at which students are taken to an agricultural training centre as field trip?”	84	200	1.40	1.41	0.82	0.78	Low
5	To what extent have students been engaged with information and communication technology (ICT training)?	84	200	1.46	1.29	0.99	0.668	Low

Grand Mean **1.37** **1.41** **0.85** **0.79**

N_1 = Number of Lecturers, N_2 = Number of Students, \bar{x}_1 = Mean of Lecturers, \bar{x}_2 = Mean of Students, SD_1 =

Standard Deviation of Lecturers SD_2 = Standard Deviation of Students

Source: Field survey, 2024

Result in Table 1 shows that all the 5 items had their Lecturers mean values ranged from 1.24 to 1.46 while the mean values of Students ranged from 1.29 to 1.57. This shows that the respondents agreed that the level of implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities is low.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Lecturers and Students on the Relationship between Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition

S/N	Item Statement	N_1	N_2	\bar{x}_1	\bar{x}_2	SD_1	SD_2	Remarks
2	Planning	84	200	3.38	3.22	0.51	0.59	Agree
3	Business	84	200	3.44	3.26	0.57	0.65	Agree
4	Communication	84	200	3.45	3.28	0.68	0.72	Agree
5	Critical and creative thinking	84	200	3.47	3.30	0.58	0.64	Agree
6	Management	84	200	3.39	3.23	0.61	0.68	Agree
7	Leadership skills	84	200	3.38	3.22	0.51	0.59	Agree
Grand Mean				3.42	3.25	0.57	0.65	

N_1 = Number of Lecturers, N_2 = Number of Students, \bar{x}_1 = Mean of Lecturers, \bar{x}_2 = Mean of Students, SD_1 =

Standard Deviation of Lecturers SD_2 = Standard Deviation of Students

Source: Field survey, 2024

Result in Table 2 shows that all the 5 items had their Lecturers mean values ranged from 3.38 to 3.47 while the mean values of Students ranged from 3.22 to 3.30. This implies that there is a relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial skills acquisition.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Lecturers and Students on the Challenges affecting Full Implementation of Entrepreneurship Education in Universities

S/N	Item Statement	N_1	N_2	\bar{x}_1	\bar{x}_2	SD_1	SD_2	Remarks
1	Under-funding	84	200	3.39	3.18	0.92	0.97	Agree
2	Lack of facilities and equipment	84	200	3.42	3.37	0.89	0.79	Agree
3	Lack of awareness	84	200	3.39	3.18	0.84	0.90	Agree
4	Lack of motivation within the institutions	84	200	3.40	3.26	0.93	0.99	Agree
5	Poor orientation by parents and lecturers	84	200	3.29	3.10	0.74	0.81	Agree
6	Lack of cooperation between the school and the indigenous	84	200	2.93	3.14	1.05	0.78	Agree
Grand Mean				3.31	3.20	0.89	0.87	

N_1 = Number of Lecturers, N_2 = Number of Students, \bar{x}_1 = Mean of Lecturers, \bar{x}_2 = Mean of Students, SD_1 =

Standard Deviation of Lecturers SD_2 = Standard Deviation of Students

Source: Field survey, 2024

Result in Table 3 shows that all the 5 items had their Lecturers mean values ranged from 2.93 to 3.42 while the mean values of Students ranged from 3.10 to 3.37. This is an indication that the items are challenges affecting full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities.

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Lecturers and Students on the Strategies for enhancing Full Implementation of Entrepreneurship Education in Universities

S/N	Item Statement	N ₁	N ₂	\bar{x}_1	\bar{x}_2	SD ₁	SD ₂	Remarks
1	Curriculum review	84	200	3.32	3.12	0.89	0.93	Agee
2	Promotion of the development and sustenance of entrepreneurs centers and centers of excellence	84	200	3.15	3.15	0.99	0.92	Agee
3	Promotion of science, technology and innovation by providing incentives for students' and lecturers	84	200	3.13	2.93	0.98	0.98	Agee
4	Sensitization, advocacy and mobilization of support for entrepreneurship education	84	200	3.45	3.23	0.59	0.73	Agee
5	Programme focus	84	200	3.49	3.26	0.77	0.87	Agee
6	Adequate funding	84	200	3.44	3.39	0.75	0.66	Agee
Grand Mean				3.33	3.18	0.83	0.85	

N₁ = Number of Lecturers, N₂ = Number of Students, \bar{x}_1 = Mean of Lecturers, \bar{x}_2 = Mean of Students, SD₁ =

Standard Deviation of Lecturers SD₂= Standard Deviation of Students

Source: Field survey, 2024

Result in Table 4 shows that all the 5 items had their Lecturers mean values ranged from 3.13 to 3.49 while the mean values of Students ranged from 3.13 to 3.39. This is means that the items are strategies for enhancing full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities.

Table 5: T-Test Result on the Level of Implementation of Entrepreneurship Education in Universities

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference			
	F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	5.689	.018	-.641	282	.522	-.03995	.06232	-.16262	.08271
Equal variances not assumed			-.558	119.103	.578	-.03995	.07159	-.18170	.10180

Source: Field survey, 2024

Result presented in Table 5 reveals a p-value is .522 with 382 degree of freedom. This implies that the difference in mean values of Lecturers and Students on the level of implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities is not statistically significant at 0.05 level.

Table 6: Regression Analysis Result on the Relationship between Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.039	.014		2.845	.005
Planning	.676	.023	.721	29.968	.000
Communication	.598	.024	.718	25.068	.000
Critical and creative thinking	.784	.036	.829	21.813	.000
Management	-.023	.018	-.026	-1.244	.214
Leadership skills	.524	.008	.506	62.378	.000
R	.998 ^a				
R Square	.997				
Adjusted R	.997				
F	.16809.118				

a. Dependent Variable: Entrepreneurship Education

Source: Field survey, 2024

The result in Table 6 shows that variation in entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial skills was explained by independent variables included in the regression model as indicated by the R² (0.998). The result shows that variation in the entrepreneurial skills was impacted for by entrepreneurship education. Result of the analysis also shows that the coefficient of planning, communication, critical and creative thinking, and leadership were significant and positively related to entrepreneurship education. This implies that entrepreneurship education enhances acquisition of entrepreneurial skills.

Table 7: T-Test Result on the Challenges affecting Full Implementation of Entrepreneurship Education in Universities

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	5.947	.015	2.199	282	.029	.17993	.08181	.01890	.34097
Equal variances not assumed			2.327	177.654	.021	.17993	.07733	.02734	.33253

Source: Field survey, 2024

Result presented in Table 7 reveals a p-value is .029 with 382 degree of freedom. This implies that the difference in mean values of Lecturers and Students on the challenges affecting full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities is statistically significant at 0.05 level.

Table 8: T-Test Result on the Strategies for Enhancing Full Implementation of Entrepreneurship Education in Universities

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
	F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	5.000	.026	2.068	282	.040	.15333	.07415	.00737	.29929
Equal variances not assumed			2.191	178.196	.030	.15333	.07000	.01520	.29147

Source: Field survey, 2024

Result presented in Table 8 reveals a p-value is .040 with 382 degree of freedom. This implies that the difference in mean values of Lecturers and Students on the strategies for enhancing full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities is not statistically significant at 0.05 level

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Result of finding of the study revealed that the level at which entrepreneurship education is implemented in universities in North Central, Nigeria is very low. The universities do not adequately recommend students to National Directorate of Employment (NDE) for training. The level of students' participation in Industrial Attachment or Student Industrial Working Experience Scheme (SIWES), at vocational and technical training, agricultural training centre as field trip", information and communication technology (ICT training) is low. The finding affirms a report by Ubogu (2013) who noted that universities in Nigeria do not fully implement entrepreneurship education due to lingering challenges.

Findings of the study also revealed a significant relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial skills such as planning, business, communication, critical and creative thinking, management and leadership skills. The finding agrees with Boma, Godpower and Kire (2019) who believed that entrepreneurship education opens the mind of people to acquire the right ideas, skills and managerial ability that will help in job creation. The finding also collaborates that of Ukata and Adejola (2018) who reported that the introduction of entrepreneurship education is worldly accepted as one of the greatest instruments for achieving economic and development as well as employment creation. Similarly, entrepreneurship education is included education curriculum because of its importance in developing and growing the economy.

Similarly, the findings revealed challenges affecting full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in North Central, Nigeria. These included under-funding, lack of facilities and equipment, lack of awareness, lack of motivation within the institutions, poor attitude to teaching and learning the skills, poor orientation by parents and lecturers and lack of cooperation between the school and the indigenious. The finding agrees with Ubogu (2013) who noted that under-funding undermines the quality entrepreneurship education; facilities such as teaching materials, equipment, laboratories and workshops; awareness and motivation within the institutions; and dearth of lecturers of entrepreneurship also stampedes entrepreneurship education.

The findings revealed strategies for enhancing full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in North Central, Nigeria. These include curriculum review; promotion of the development and sustenance of entrepreneurship centers and centers of excellence; promotion of science, technology and innovation by providing incentives for students' and lecturers; sensitization, advocacy and mobilization of support for entrepreneurship education; programme focus; and adequate funding. The finding supports that of Ubogu (2011) who asserted that targeting the universities for spinning off entrepreneurship spirit and culture is a good strategy for full implementation of entrepreneurship education in all universities. Also, the finding agrees with Azuka and Azuka (2013) listed the strategies to achieve a functional entrepreneurship education for national development. These include adoption of innovative methods to train teachers in entrepreneurship; setting up of short-term exchanges of entrepreneurship teachers between the institutions of higher education in order to disseminate best practice and teaching methods; establishment of a think tank group; and introduction to entrepreneurship and self-employment should be offered as part of career guidance and establishing job creation offices in each of the states in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Entrepreneurship is considered as the engine power of economic development and growth of the nation. It provides solution to skills challenges affecting business activities. There is a significant relationship between entrepreneurship education and skills acquisition. However, the study has established low implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in the North Central, Nigeria due to numerous challenges. The study concludes that appropriate strategies could be adopted to enhance full implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in the North Central, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The management of universities in the North Central, Nigeria should ensure that students are adequately recommend students to National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Industrial Attachment or Student Industrial Working Experience Scheme (SIWES), vocational and technical training, agricultural training centre as field trip”, information and communication technology (ICT training) as supportive effort toward entrepreneurship education
2. The universities should place much emphasis on entrepreneurship education considering the fact that it serves as a tool for entrepreneurial skills acquisition
3. The government should ensure that entrepreneurship education is properly funded for enhanced entrepreneurial skills acquisition
4. The universities should adopt innovative methods to train teachers in entrepreneurship who will teach the students the required entrepreneurial skills.

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